

Acute and Chronic Complications in Partially Treated Steroid-Resistant Nephrotic Syndrome in Resource-Limited Settings: An Evidence-Based Case Report

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Article History:

Received: 11.03.2025 Revised: 18.04.2025 Accepted: 22.04.2025 Published: 27.04.2025

Abstract

Introduction. Steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome (SRNS) is a major cause of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in children and later in adolescents. The proper management involves pediatrician, nephrologist, nurses, family, health insurance, and family. Every region in Indonesia has a specific challenges in managing SRNS. The present case is a portrait of some difficulties in treating SRNS in some province referral hospital in Indonesia. **Case report.** We report the children with SRNS, accompanied by some difficulties that are harmful for his present, and also future. Comprehensive approach is absolutely needed in achieving better prognosis. We provide some evidence-based approach in managing the patient. **Conclusion.** Proper SRNS treatment from the clinician, collaborative support from the family, government, and health-insurance is very essential.

Keywords: *Chronic kidney disease, Steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome, complications management, children.*

Suggested citation: Widiasta, A. (2025). Acute and Chronic Complications in Partially Treated Steroid-Resistant Nephrotic Syndrome in Resource-Limited Settings: An Evidence-Based Case Report. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(3), 102-109. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(3\).09](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(3).09)

Introduction

Nephrotic syndrome in children causes complications, both acute and chronic. Acute complications include infection, deep vein thrombosis, and hypertension. Hypertension in children results largely from secondary causes, with kidney disease (60-70%) and renovascular disease being the most common causes (Flynn et al., 2017). Acute complications if inadequate management has an impact on mortality, while chronic complications have an impact on chronic kidney disease (CKD) and progression into end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). In some developing countries, sometimes the management of these complications encounters various obstacles, especially limited facilities and

medicines. This case report will show various problems that occur in the management of NS complications, as well as management that can be maximized despite these limitations.

Case Report

A 9-years-old boy brought to the hospital with a chief complaint of generalized tonic-clonic seizure 8 h prior to admission. Seizure occurred five times within one hour, each lasting for about three minutes, followed by a decrease in level of consciousness. The seizure was preceded by sudden headache, blurred vision, and vomiting without fever. The seizure was accompanied by swelling of the face, abdomen, and legs. He had experienced two episodes of similar seizures at 3 months and 1 year prior to admission. He was

diagnosed with SRNS 1 year prior to admission and had completed seven cycles of intravenous cyclophosphamide 5 months prior to admission. He routinely came to Nephrology Out-patient Clinic and continued taking medicine; cyclosporine A, alternate dose methylprednisolone, captopril, Spironolactone, vitamin D3, and calcium carbonate.

On general examination, he appeared severely ill, somnolent, and had generalized edema. The vital signs included hypertension and tachycardia. Neurological examination suggested an upper motor neuron lesion with increased physiological reflexes, positive Babinski sign, clonus, increased muscle tone, and no paresis. Laboratory examination revealed moderate anemia (10,6 g/dL), leukocytosis (29.030/mm³), increased CRP (2.08 mg/dL), and hypoalbuminemia (2.17 g/dL), with a normal estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) 99.8 mL/min/1.73 m². Urinalysis revealed proteinuria (+3) and hematuria (+1). Microscopically, the erythrocyte count was 5.5/hpf, quantitative 24-hours protein urine was 3.769 g. The urine protein/creatinine ratio was 10, and the cyclosporine parent level was high 348.6 ng/mL. The patient was diagnosed with hypertensive encephalopathy (I67.4), SRNS (N04.3), CKD Stage I (N18.1), anemia due to chronic disease (D63.8), Cushing syndrome (E24.9), and underimmunization (Z28.3).

The problems of this patient are divided into: (1) problem related to diagnostic plan and management, i.e. Establish the diagnosis and management of hypertensive encephalopathy and etiology of steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome; perform head CT scan, kidney biopsy, C3 complement; fluid requirement, adequate nutrition intake with low salt and protein intake. (2)

Problem related to prognostic was patients' quality of life, possibility of remission, complications of hypertensive encephalopathy, nephrotic syndrome, chronic kidney disease, and response to therapy. (3) Problem related to management of complication was providing adequate education about the complication of the diseases.

The management of these patients was classified into (1) Emergency Management, that is, stabilization management of the airway, breathing, circulation, and hospitalization. (2) Management of hypertensive encephalopathy: nicardipine 1 mcg/kg/minute, clonidine 1 mcg/kg/24 hours ~ 25 mcg every 24 hours via nasogastric tube (NGT) (titrated dose), captopril (12.5 mg) every 12 hours via NGT, Phenobarbital 220 mg i. v. (loading dose), and 50 mg every 12 h i.v. Additionally, the management of SRNS, that is, Methylprednisolone alternate dose 32 mg every 48 hours tapering off 16 mg every 48 hours via NGT. Change cyclosporine to tacrolimus 1 mg every 12 hours via NGT, transfusion of albumin 20% 1 g/kg ~ 100 mL i.v., spironolactone 25 mg every 24 hours via NGT, and (3) Management of CKD, divided into conservative and substitution therapy. Conservative therapy includes the management of adequate nutrition, maintenance of fluid and electrolyte balance, administration of appropriate doses, and kind of medicine. Substitution therapy included calcium carbonate 500 mg every 24 h via NGT, Vitamin D3 2000 IU every 24 h via NGT. Nutritional Management: Calories requirement Resting Energy Expenditure (REE) equal to 1000 kcal/day, consisting of liquid diet 125 ml every 3 hours per day, protein 1 g/kg/day ~ 22 g/day, and low salt diet (maximum 2 g/day). Monitoring management includes observation of the general condition and vital signs (blood pressure), work of breathing, edema, fluid intake, diuresis, nutritional intake, and monitoring for other possible signs and symptoms of seizure, alteration of consciousness, and other complications in multiple organs due to the progression of hypertensive emergency.

Monitoring disease-associated complications, infections, thromboembolism, hypovolemic crisis, and cardiovascular problems. Monitoring adverse effects of cytotoxic drugs (cyclosporine). Monitoring adverse effects of long-term drug therapy (corticosteroids). In addition, we planned an education plan to provide emotional support for the patient and family when facing psychological stress due to the patient's illness.

Hypertension in children is defined by Stein and Ferguson (2015) as "a systolic and/or diastolic

blood pressure (BP) equal to or exceeding the 95th percentile based on age, sex, and height in multiple measurements”. Based on severity, hypertension (HTN) is classified into stage 1 and stage 2. Stage 1 HTN is classified as systolic or diastolic BP between the 95th percentile and <95th percentile + 12 mm Hg (Baracco and Mattoo, 2014). Stage 2 HTN is systolic or diastolic BP higher than 12 mmHg above the 95th percentile (Flynn et al., 2017; Rabi et al., 2020).

Children can become symptomatic from HTN with lesser degrees of BP elevation (Flynn et al. 2017), but when BP rises above the threshold for stage 2 HTN, the patient will present with acute severe HTN. Steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome (SRNS) is a major cause of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in children, even later in adolescence. Acute severe elevation of blood pressure with evidence of target organ damage defines a hypertensive emergency, which may manifest as encephalopathy, renal impairment, heart failure or elevated liver function tests) (Rovin et al., 2021). Hypertensive emergencies in children most commonly manifest as hypertensive encephalopathy; severe elevation of blood pressure with cerebral oedema and neurological symptoms of lethargy, coma and/or seizures.

In this case, based on the anamnesis and physical and laboratory examinations, the patient was diagnosed with hypertensive encephalopathy with the clinical manifestation of seizure, blurred vision, vomiting, and decreased level of consciousness.

Discussion

Hypertension in children results largely from secondary causes, with kidney disease (60-70%) and renovascular disease being the most common causes (Flynn et al., 2017). In this case, the patient also presented with edema, massive proteinuria, hypoalbuminemia, and hyperlipidemia. He was diagnosed with SRNS one year prior and had seven cycles of cyclophosphamide (CPA), without any remission. The patient continued therapy with a calcineurin inhibitor (cyclosporine A) until hospitalization. Starcea and her colleagues (2022) defines the SRNS as “a lack of complete

remission after 4 weeks of therapy with daily glucocorticoids (prednisone or prednisolone) at a standard dose”. The recommendation of initial treatment for NS is oral glucocorticoids that can be given for 8 weeks (4 weeks of daily glucocorticoids followed by 4 weeks of alternate-day glucocorticoids) or 12 weeks (6 weeks of daily glucocorticoids followed by 6 weeks of alternate-day glucocorticoids) (Level of Evidence 1b) (Guidelinecentral, 2021). For children with SRNS, calcineurin inhibitor (CNI), such as cyclosporine A (CyA) or tacrolimus, are recommended as the initial second-line therapy after glucocorticoid failure) (Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of Evidence 1c). CPA can be used if CNI was unavailable) (Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of Evidence 1c). Retrospective review of the children with difficult-to-treat SRNS attained complete remission following intravenous CPA infusions (Haddad et al., 2021) (Level of Evidence 3b).

SRNS may be attributed to this patient's hypertension. Steroid-resistant patients had a much higher prevalence than steroid-sensitive patients (66.7 and 14.3 %, respectively) (Shatat et al., 2019). The etiology of HTN in nephrotic syndrome is multifactorial; it is related to renal and non-renal intrinsic and extrinsic/environmental factors (Shatat et al., 2019). Renal factors include sodium retention (RAAS/ renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system activation), fibrosis/loss of GFR and progression of kidney disease, and fluid shift (albuminuria) (Haas et al., 2018; Shatat et al., 2019). Shatat and his colleagues (2019) states that extra-renal factors include medication side effects (CNI, steroid), co-morbid conditions (obesity, left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), impaired glucose metabolism, hyperlipidemia), and genetic predisposition (Shatat et al., 2019). In this case, the patient showed a normal ratio of (intravenous cava (IVC/Ao), although he had proteinuria. The sodium levels were within normal limits. The patient was routinely administered an aldosterone agonist (spironolactone) routinely. Progression to CKD was unlikely, as the GFR was normal. However, the patient consumed CNI; meanwhile, the steroid dose was tapered off (alternate day). The patient also presented with hyperlipidemia

without obesity, LVH, or impaired glucose metabolism.

Posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES) may occur in patients with hypertension and underlying renal disease. However, this syndrome is rare in children. Although PRES can be present in the absence of significant hypertension, it usually occurs in hypertensive patients (Baracco and Mattoo, 2014). Based on typical clinical manifestations and neurological imaging, PRES can be diagnosed. Patients generally present with hypertensive encephalopathy, including headache, vomiting, visual disturbances, confusion, altered sensorium, and seizures. Radiologically, PRES is predominantly characterised by a symmetrical distribution of patchy or globular lesions in the white matter of the parietal and occipital lobes. Multiple cortico-subcortical hypodensities, distinct from acute infarcts or haemorrhages, are seen on head CT scans (Munirah et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2014). In this case, the patient presented with clinical signs of PRES, supported by head CT scan findings of diffuse, symmetrical, hypodense lesions in the brainstem (midbrain and pons) and bilateral subcortical frontoparietal lobes. To support the diagnosis of SRNS, whether the type of lesion is a minimal or non-minimal change, C3 complement examination should be performed. In minimal change disease, levels of complement C3 are usually normal, whereas in non-minimal change disease, C3 levels will decrease (Zamora and Pearson-Shaver, 2023) (Level of evidence 1a). In this patient, the level of C3 complement was normal, suggesting minimal change disease. However, based on clinical manifestations such as age onset, hypertensive condition, and persistent hematuria, the patient was diagnosed with non-minimal change disease. Therefore, further diagnostic evaluation is necessary. The kidney biopsy will provide information on the degree of interstitial and glomerular fibrosis, which will be used to assess the prognosis of children with SRNS (Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of Evidence 1a).

The overall goals for treating HTN in children and adolescents, including both primary and secondary HTN, include achieving a BP level that reduces the risk for target organ damage in

childhood and the risk of HTN and related CVD in adulthood (Flynn et al., 2017). The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) hypertension guidelines recommend lowering blood pressure below the 90th percentile in children aged 1 to 13 years (Bell et al., 2018; Flynn et al., 2017; Rovin et al., 2021). Children with glomerular disease should have their blood pressure controlled to the 50th percentile for systolic and diastolic blood pressure for their age and sex, using published or locally available standards (Kidney International Supplements (2011) (Level of Evidence 1a). In people with acute severe HTN, treatment with short-acting antihypertensive drugs should be started immediately and BP reduced by no more than 25% in the first 8 hours, with the remainder of the planned reduction taking place over the next 12 to 24 hours (Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of Evidence 1d).

KDIGO and AAP recommend angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE-Is) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) as first-line antihypertensive treatment for children with hypertension (Flynn et al., 2017; Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of evidence 1a). Especially in children with SN, ACE-I or ARB can be used as antiproteinuric and renoprotective agents, which may reduce proteinuria by 40–50% (Rovin et al., 2021; Stotter and Ferguson, 2019) (Level of evidence 1b). If the patient can tolerate oral therapy, treatment of acute severe HTN can be started with oral agents. Intravenous agents are indicated when oral therapy is not possible due to the clinical condition of the patient or when there are serious complications. First-line intravenous agents include nicardipine, labetalol, and esmolol, which are usually administered continuously as drops (Baracco and Mattoo, 2014). As a central alpha agonist, clonidine can be given orally in a lesser degree of crisis (Rovin et al., 2021) (Level of evidence 2a). Nicardipine is commonly used in hypertensive emergency in children. It is a rapid-acting calcium channel blocker (CCB) that decreases BP by inducing vascular smooth muscle relaxation and vasodilation, mainly in the arteries, thus decreasing peripheral vascular resistance (Baracco and Mattoo, 2014; Partigiani et al., 2022; Raina et al., 2020). In this case, we used

nicardipine drip 1 µg/kg/minute, ACE-I, that is, captopril at a dose of 0.3 – 0.5 mg/kgBW/dose twice daily, and Clonidine 2 mcg/kg/day via nasogastric tube. The patient also received an anticonvulsant (phenobarbital) because of a history of status epilepticus. The Neurocritical Care Society (2012) defines status epilepticus as “a seizure with 5 minutes or more of continuous clinical and/or electrographic seizure activity or recurrent seizure activity without recovery between seizures”. Status epilepticus may lead to permanent brain damage (Brophy et al., 2012). In this case, considering the seizure secondary to acute HTN due to SRNS, the patient was at risk of recurrent seizures as long as the BP remained uncontrolled. Therefore, the patient was administered a loading dose of phenobarbital and the maintenance dose was continued intravenously (Level of evidence 3).

Albumin infusion should be administered with caution, and the patient should be closely monitored for complications, such as hypertension, volume overload, pulmonary edema, and congestive heart failure. The retrospective study showed a significant improvement was noted in all of the patient following co-administration of albumin and furosemide without any adverse events (Latief et al., 2021). In this patient, there were severe edema and we gave albumin transfusion following furosemide injection (Level of Evidence 3).

For the treatment of hyperlipidaemia in children with NS, there are no clear guidelines. Hyperlipidemia generally improves once NS is in remission (Shatat et al., 2019). The KDIGO guidelines state that hyperlipidemia in NS should be treated in accordance with the guidelines for high-risk individuals at risk of developing cardiovascular disease, especially if the disease cannot be improved. HDL cholesterol levels are influenced by statins, fibrates, nicotinic acid, and cholesteryl ester transfer protein inhibitors (Agrawal et al., 2018; Hari et al., 2020). Nevertheless, statins did not improve the remission rate and did not reduce the risk of major cardiovascular events or initiation of kidney replacement therapy in non-diabetic nephrotic patients (Busuioac et al., 2023). In this case, no dietary fat restriction or

pharmacotherapy was prescribed because the child was only 9 years old, dyslipidemia screening was only performed once, fasting glucose and HbA1c levels and echocardiography were normal, and uPCR levels showed improvement (Level of Evidence 1a).

To lower blood pressure, lifestyle interventions are recommended. The Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) programme recommends specific elements of this diet as the primary dietary strategy that has been tested in the literature. These elements include a diet high in fruits, vegetables, low-fat dairy products, whole grains, fish, poultry, nuts and lean red meat; limited intake of sugar and sweets; and low sodium intake (<2,300 g per day) (Flynn et al. (2017); National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (2025). Meanwhile KDIGO recommends lesser sodium intake (<2g/day) (Rovin et al., 2021). In this patient, the diet was prescribed in accordance with the DASH guidelines for children with kidney disease (Level of Evidence 2c).

In children with frequently relapsing nephrotic syndrome or SRNS, a reduction in bone mineral content can be prevented by oral supplementation with oral calcium and vitamin D (Rovin et al., 2021). In patients with CKD, vitamin D deficiency may contribute to worsening kidney function and increased morbidity and mortality. These renoprotective effects of vitamin D treatment go well beyond its classical role in maintaining bone and mineral metabolism, in addition to its pleiotropic effects on extra-mineral metabolism (Hsu et al., 2020; Kim and Kim, 2014) (Level of evidence 1b). In this case, we prescribed Vitamin D3 2000 IU every 24 hour and Calcium carbonate 500 mg every 24 hours orally.

Associated with survival in children with SRNS were age at onset, initial renal function, onset of hypertension and type of resistance. Children with SRNS are more likely to develop doubling of baseline creatinine levels and end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). Age, initial kidney function, hypertension at onset, and type of hypertension were all considered. In this case, the prognosis for *quo ad vitam* is *dubia ad bonam* because the complication that occurred was acute severe

hypertension causing recurrent seizure complications that need to be treated with appropriate medication (CNI), whereas other severe complications such as shortness of breath, thrombosis, and hypovolemic shock were not observed in the patient. Due to persistent proteinuria and hypertension, but the eGFR is still within normal limits, there are no known hereditary factors and the age of onset is between 1 year and 10 years, the prognosis for *quo ad functionam* is *dubia ad bonam*. However, further studies are needed to assess the responsiveness to therapy and histopathological study results. The prognosis of *quo ad sanationam* is *dubia ad bonam* because patients fail to achieve proteinuria remission with medications other than corticosteroids. Proteinuria is a predictor of poor outcome and progression to ESRD. Patients with SRNS 36%–50% progressing to ESKD within 10 years (Nourbakhsh and Mak, 2017).

Conclusion

Family and patient adherence to treatment are absolutely crucial because inadequate treatment results in unresolved remission and may alter the stage of CKD. Physicians must be able to educate the patient's parents properly, provide adequate information about the patient's illness and the treatment plan to be followed, and motivate the patient to comply with the treatment. The patient's family understood the patient's condition and cooperated with the patient during treatment. Families are involved in the monitoring of therapies.

Acknowledgement

Intan Risna, M.D., Prof Dany Hilmanto, M.D., Ph.D., Prof. Dedi Rachmadi, M.D., Ph.D., Fina Mellyana, M.D., Stanza Uga Peryoga, M.D., Dzulfikar Djalil, M.D., Ph.D., Dadang Hudaya, M.D., Ph.D., and allof the nurses in pediatric ward and PICU for treating the patient.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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